

The Graduates of College of Business Administration of Assumption College of Nabunturan: A tracer Study

ILLEYT R. SILVA

<http://orcid.org/0000-0002-4927-0904>

Assumption College of Nabunturan

Nabunturan, Compostela Valley

ABSTRACT: This tracer study provides an access to understanding the stature of the College of Business Administration of the Assumption College of Nabunturan in terms of reasons why the graduate chose A C N, the skills and competency honed and displayed in the workplace, employment and further studies taken. A descriptive exploratory study employing random sampling to determine its respondents, validity of responses was gauged at 30% - 60% response rate. The study found out that the alumni's top four reasons in enrolling to A C N were location, opportunities for career advancement, competitive faculty and influence of parents. Further, the study revealed that 35% of the respondents are presently connected with the government sector and 65% are in the private institutions, while 7% are unemployed. Majority of those employed alumni or 46% were holding clerical position while a significant number of them or 22% were in the supervisory or managerial functions. Human relations, Communication, and Entrepreneurial were the skills dominantly performed by the alumni in the workplace.

Keywords: Tracer Study, Alumni, Skills and Competencies, Descriptive Exploratory, College of Business Management, Assumption College of Nabunturan, Philippines

I. Introduction

A nation's competitiveness is founded on the emergence and capability of its human capital and that the essence of knowledge, skills and capability of an economy emanates from its people. To keep pace with the fast changing education brought by technology and globalization, higher educational institution must continuously assess its product and service delivery to its client. Cruz and Alcantara (2014) echoed that higher education institutions should pursue tracer studies for the reasons of instituting value, purpose and excellence to the course or programs within. Moreover, tracer studies generate valuable information, empirically generated so that appropriate assessment to curriculum development is established (Aquino, Punongbayan, Macalaguim, Bauyon, Rodriguez, Jr. and Quizon, 2016).

Higher educational institution's key to developing a responsive program needed by the society is to provide a well-defined outline of information strategically in line with its vision, mission and core competencies. To keep this challenge, Assumption College of Nabunturan must upkeep to the mandate of the Commission on Higher Education's theme of instilling and nurturing the student's qualities and skills requisite to leadership and success (Abergos, Minlano, Ramos, Daraway and De Vera, 2008).

The immediate growth to competition spews a greater perspective of creating programs equipped of transforming students to be highly responsive, innovative and competitive in the field, hence, Cruz and Alcantara (2014) purposely reiterated that college institutions should offer up to date curriculum that enhances skills needed for employment, strengthen their knowledge on the skills available and improve their ability and articulation.

Gines (2014) presented that a tracer study is an attempt to acknowledge target groups for the purposes of evaluating effective and ineffective strategies. Further, Abergos, et al (2008) echoed that graduate tracer study (GTS)

becomes a mechanism to improve programs, and alleviate faculty performance to conform to the requirement set by the government and perhaps, employment. The Bachelor of Science in Commerce / Bachelor of Science in Business Administration has been one of the core courses offered by the Assumption College of Nabunturan and one of the three courses accredited Level 2 by the Philippine Association of Accrediting Schools, Colleges and Universities (PAASCU).

The study is conducted to provide Assumption College of Nabunturan empirically processed study on the whereabouts of its graduate. More so, present the deepness of this endeavor in such a way that this provides descriptive information and analysis to further enhance its strategic set up and formulate competency and skilled related programs that would allow its clients to be responsive on the trends among industries' need of human resources. The College of Business Administration of Assumption College of Nabunturan refers to the Bachelor of Science in Commerce (BSC) and Bachelor of Science in Business Administration.

This study takes into consideration the significance of a GTS to further improve Assumption College of Nabunturan's desire to effectively offer programs suitable to what the society needs, competitively produce quality graduates and establish strong partnership and linkages to entities and businesses within the municipality, province, and country and around the globe.

Research Objectives

The study attempts to present an empirical description of the graduates of Assumption College of Nabunturan under the Bachelor of Science in Commerce / Bachelor of Science in Business Administration for the school years 2005 – 2018. Specifically, the study ought to provide the following;

1. Determine the reason/s why the BSC / BSBA Alumni enrolled in Assumption College of Nabunturan
2. Trace the employment profile of the graduates
3. Identify the competencies displayed by the graduates on their present employment

II. Methods

Research Design

The study used descriptive and exploratory research in tracing the BSC / BSBA graduates of A C N from 2005 – 2018. Purposive sampling was the basis of getting the sample. The method allowed the researcher to impose equal chances among respondents to be chosen and at the same time distinctively present a reliable and valid study.

Research Respondents

Gines (2014) echoed Schomburg (2003) literature that for purposes of validity, population size or the number responses should fall within the expected response rate of 30 to 60 percentages. A total of 560 graduates were identified of which the sample was derived. A total of 195 alumni responded to the data gathering conducted by the researcher using google forms.

Research Instrument

The researcher adopted the tracer study questionnaire developed by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). Further modification was done in the tracer survey questionnaire (TSQ) as the study focuses more on demography, reasons why the alumni enrolled in the school, line of business where the graduate is currently employed, employment status, pursued further studies / advancement and competencies utilized in the workplace.

Research Procedure

The researcher firstly, asked the coordinator of the RDPC of A C N to conduct GTS among BSC / BSBA graduates. Taking into consideration the academic dimension of the study, the researcher then asked the permission of the Dean of College and the program head of the College of Business Administration. Through the online medium, the research sent private messages to the graduates asking their availability and willingness to participate in the said endeavor.

Statistical Treatment

To sequentially present the output of the study, the researcher primarily used frequency counts, percentages, mean and rankings. Interpretations of means shall be based on a 5 - point Likert scale.

On Reasons why the respondents enrolled in A C N

Scale	Description	Interpretation
1.00	1.8 Very Low	The respondent does not view the factor as a significant reason
1.81	2.61 Low	The respondent views the factor but not significant
2.62	3.41 Moderate	The respondent views the factor as somewhat significant
3.42	4.22 High	The respondent views the factor as significant
4.23	5.00 Very High	The respondent views the factor as very significant

On skills and competencies displayed

Scale	Description	Interpretation
1.00	1.8 Very Low	Skill and Competencies are not displayed
1.81	2.61 Low	Skill and Competencies are somewhat not displayed
2.61	3.41 Moderate	Skill and Competencies are somewhat displayed
3.42	4.22 High	Skill and Competencies are displayed
4.23	5.00 Very High	Skill and Competencies are highly displayed

III. Results and Discussion

This chapter offers the result of the study where frequency counts, ranking, mean interpretations were presented based on the collated data retrieved from the responses of the respondents. More so, an endeavor is offered in this chapter that highlights the quantitative outcome that measures the relevant information of this tracer study among the graduates of Assumption College of Nabunturan under the Commerce program and College of Business Administration, school years 2005 – 2006 to 2017 – 2018.

A total of 195 respondents were gathered or 35% of the total number of graduates from 2005 - 2006 to 2017 –2018.

Table 1. Demographic profile of the Respondents

Gender	Relative Frequency	Frequency count	Civil Status	Relative Frequency	Frequency count
Male	39%	76	Single	73%	142
Female	61%	119	Married	27%	53
Total	100%	195		100%	195

Table 1 is presented the distribution of respondents by Gender and Civil Status. Further, the data showed that 61% or 119 of the respondents were female while 39% or 76 were males. The response by gender clearly showed the responsive rate among female graduates were high and tracer studies were venues among them in displaying advantages to employment and status. More so, 73% or 142 are single and 27% or 53 are married, this means that majority of the participants are those who graduated within the last 5 years and are still in the age bracket of 20 – 25 years old.

Table 2. Ranking on the reasons why the Alumni enrolled in A C N

Rank	Reason	Mean Score	Description
1	Location	4.51	Very High
2	Prospect for Career Advancement	3.97	High
3	Competitive Faculty	3.96	High
4	Parent’s Influence	3.94	High
5	Strong passion to the course	3.68	High
6	Inspired by a Role Model	3.34	Moderate
7	Peer Influence	3.13	Moderate
8	Affordable tuition fee	3.11	Moderate

Table 2 offered the list of factors that influenced the graduates as to why they enrolled in Assumption College of Nabunturan. The study revealed that, out of the eight factors, Location has the highest mean score of 4.51. This, in a way is understandable as parents or even the graduates themselves find more opportunities and advantages when colleges or universities are within their locality. Spearman, Abdul Rahim, Ghanayem and Ljepava (2016) offered that location is a vital factor in deciding where to pursue college education.

Prospect for career development and competitive faculty comes second and third with mean scores of 3.97 and 3.96, respectively. The responses of the alumni captured that intense curriculum and continuous improvement of Assumption College of Nabunturan in delivering a proactive commerce / business administration program, manifested by a responsive teaching personnel pursued with expertise in offering a course needed by industries in general.

Influences of parents and peers (ranked 4 and 7) are factors which could be attributed to experience by these stakeholders. A generally viable academic environment perceived by these people is vehemently an advantage as this denotes the desire of people to market the school, directly or indirectly.

Strong Passion to the course and Influenced by a role model (ranked 5 and 6) are significant responses as these categorically puts the institution as an interface to delivery of appropriate skills and competencies needed by industries and even in government. More so, Business Administration courses is one of those easily chosen by students hence, able to provide the appropriate academic requirement tantamount to allowing the students realized the course significance.

Affordable Tuition fee is the least influencing factor with a mean score of 3.11. This somehow is common sense, as school payments are perceived to be burdens among the students and that in the 10 year period, tuition fee increased by 50% - 60%, approximately.

Table 3. Distribution of Further Studies and professional examination taken and passed by the Alumni

Further Studies	Relative Frequency	Frequency count	Professional Examination passed	Relative Frequency	Frequency Count
Master’s Degree (MBA / MM)	4%	8	Civil Service Level 1	2%	4
Education Units	23%	45	Civil Service Level 2	7%	14
None	73%	142	LET	9%	18
			PNP / AFP	7%	16
			None	75%	146
Total	100%	195		100%	195

Table 3 offered the effort of the alumni to pursue further studies as this manifest earnest desire to have more decent employment opportunities and at the same time higher chances of promotion, land a better job position and high salary. Furthermore, the study revealed that 4% of the respondents took a degree in either Master in Management or Master in Business Administration. Twenty three percent or 45 of them took Education units as a response to the

growing needs of the basic education department specifically the Department of Education in its implementation of the K-12 curriculum where our graduates' mastery in the Accountancy, Business and Management is a necessity. Seventy three percent or 142 of the Alumni have not taken any of the degrees.

Moreover, 2% or 4 alumni had taken and passed the Civil Service level 1 Examination (Sub Professional) and 7% or 14 of them had taken and passed the CS level 2 exams (Professional Examination). Civil Service examination is considered to be one of the most difficult examinations of the country and that this is a necessary requirement to those who are employed in the government. Nine percent had taken and passed the Licensure Examination for Teachers, seven percent took the PNP / AFP Exams and passed while seventy five percent or 146 alumni had not taken any of the examinations.

Table 4. Distribution of Employment and Reasons for Unemployment

Employment Status	Relative Frequency	Frequency Count
Employed	93%	181
Unemployed	7%	14
Total	100%	195
Reasons for Unemployment		
Reasons	Relative Frequency	Frequency Count
Further Studies	10%	1
Family Concern	80%	12
No Job Opportunity	10%	1

Presented in table 4 the employment status of the alumni where 93% or 181 alumni are now presently employed while 7% are unemployed. To note, those alumni that were unemployed had given their reasons, to wit, 1 of the 14 alumni or 10% took at present further studies while another 10% or 1 of the 14 alumni responded about lack of job opportunity. Meanwhile, 12 of the 14 who are unemployed replied that their being unemployed is due to concerns in the family; this somehow is an indication of alumni who are now parents and chose to personally take care their household and children.

Table 5. Distribution of Institutions where the Alumni are employed

Institution	Relative Frequency	Frequency Count
Government	35%	63
Private Sector	65%	118
Total	100%	195

Table 5 is shown the distribution of institution where the graduates are employed. It was found out that the Commerce / Business Administration programs provides the needed labor needs of both the government and the private sector where 35% or 63 of them are in the government service while 65% or 118 are in the private sector.

Table 6. Distribution of Agencies where the Alumni is presently employed in Government

Government	Relative Frequency	Frequency Count
Enforcement (PNP / AFP)	7%	4
Local Government Units	29%	18
Government Owned and Controlled Corporation	30%	19
National Agencies	21%	13
DepEd	12%	8
Total	100%	63

Alumni’s present affiliation among the government agencies is presented in Table 6 where it was revealed that 30% of those in the government are connected with the GOCCs, either in SSS, GSIS, Pag – IbigFund, PhilHealth and others. Twenty nine percent are in the LGU (Province, Municipal / City and Barangay), twenty one percent are in the National Agencies, 12% are connected with the Department of Education and seven percent or 4 of the respondents are in the active service in either the PNP or AFP.

Table 7. Distribution of Affiliated Industries where the Alumni are employed in the Private sector

Industry	Relative Frequency	Frequency Count
Banking and Finance	31%	37
Marketing	27%	32
Business Process Outsourcing	7%	8
Agriculture and Fisheries	3%	4
Water and Electric Utilities	6%	7
Academic Institution	6%	7
Construction	6%	7
Total	100%	118

Table 7 offers the alumni’s affiliated industries in the private sector. Thirty one percent of the graduates are presently employed in the banking and finance, twenty seven percent in marketing. The result clearly provides the responsiveness of the BSBA / Commerce programs as the curriculum focuses in both financial and operation management. Moreover, seven percent or 8 of the total 118 alumni are in the BPO industry as call center agents. Three were in the fisheries and Agriculture sector, Water and Electric utilities, Academic Institutions and Construction with six percent each.

With the result given, GTS is a method of providing a glimpse of effective academic implementation especially among its business graduates, Velasco et al (2014) pointed about the competency developed by HEIs and how this could contribute to the industry’s human resources, and that, filling the gap is a milestone that A C N is able deliver a true product. Furthermore, the human capital as a substantial requirement to development must be the significant subject in deepening skills cognizant to what the industry needs (Abel and Dietz, 2012).

Table 8. Distribution of Employment Status and Job Description

Employment Status	Relative Frequency	Frequency Count	Job Description	Relative Frequency	Frequency Count
Regular / Permanent	53%	94	Police / AFP Officer	2%	4
Probationary / Casual	14%	31	Rank and file / Clerical	46%	86
Contractual / Job Order	43%	43	Supervisory / managerial	22%	40
Self Employed	6%	11	Customer Relations	22%	40
			Others	8%	14
Total	100%	181		100%	181

Table 8 provided the alumni’s employment status and position held. It was revealed that majority of the graduates or fifty threepercentare in their regular or permanent status, although it can be noted that forty six percent are holding clerical positions. Forty three percent or 43 of the 181 respondents are in the contractual / Job order status. Fourteen percent are in the probationary / casual status and 6% are self - employed.

In addition, table 8 presents the held positions of the alumni where, as mentioned forty six percent are holding clerical positions. Supervisory and managerial positions alongside with client relations have twenty two percent of the

respondents and eight percent for other position held as this implies that some of the alumni operates their own business.

The role of HEI's is not just providing an adequate academic environment but to ensure its graduates employability. Hence, Gines (2014) presented a dimension about GTS as attempting to evaluate effective strategy and that employment status and description clearly defines the effective delivery of the academic requirements set by institutions, either in government or private sector.

Table 9. Ranking of Skills and Competencies displayed by the Alumni

Rank	Skill and Competency	Mean Score	Description
1	Human Relations	4.17	high
2	Communication	4.02	high
3	Entrepreneurial	3.9	high
4	Problem Solving	3.87	high
5	Leadership and Management	3.85	high
6	Critical Thinking	3.79	high

Table 9 offered the ranking of the skills and competencies displayed by the alumni in the workplace. The displayed competencies were those skills where the graduates acquired as a result of their training in the school. It was noted that Human relations and Communication skills have the highest mean score of 4.17 and 4.02, respectively. While the competencies' such as Entrepreneurial, Problem solving, Leadership and Management and Critical thinking have a descriptive mean scores of high.

Although, the data provides a satisfactory responses from the alumni but a glaring need to substantially create a more proactive curriculum that enhances a more competitive graduates should be the basis. Segismundo and Zacarias (2017) noted that institutions must have a strict monitoring of the movements of its graduates so that effective and efficient improvement is taken such that the standards among industries are changing. Aquino et al (2015) on the one hand talks about conniving with industries for the aim of continuously developing the school's curricula responsive to the stirring needs of the society.

IV. Discussion

This graduate tracer study among the Commerce / BSBA graduates of Assumption College in Nabunturan is a significant endeavor aimed to present the needed information as to the whereabouts and employment conditions of the graduates. More so, it attempted to come up with as valid output offering relevant information that tackles the reason why they enrolled in Assumption College of Nabunturan, the prevalence of employment, unemployment and further studies taken and lastly, the competencies and skills displayed by the graduates in the workplace.

Reasons Why the Graduate Enrolled in Assumption College of Nabunturan

Enrolling in A C N as mentioned by the graduates is influenced primarily by location although the factor seemed to preview practicality; Sia Kee Ming (2010) offered that nearness as a major indicator to students' choice and consistency of attending classes. Career advancement and competitive faculty were recognized to be of significance to decisions as these denote conduciveness to learning environment. More so, Paulsen (1990) noted that students are inclined more to outcomes and by a delivering faculty grows a potent passion to the course essential to forming career opportunities. Further added that students tend to purview where the graduates go after graduation and further opportunities encountered.

Influence by parents mirrorsthe graduates' dependence especially to parents as they provide the funding to education (Bhayani, 2015). More so, susceptibilityto social influence especially by peers as this implies direct or indirect referencing to service delivery and responsiveness (Dahl, Manchanda and Argo, 2001). Lastly, tuition fee found to be least significant among the graduates as Sia Kee Ming (2010) clearly noted about costs as a negative influencer among college students.

Prevalence of Employment, Unemployment, Further Studies, and skills and competencies displayed in the workplace

High degree of acceptance was established in the paper, being able to provide the necessary skills and competencies, A C N relishes a concurring achievement of enabling its graduates to land jobs manifested by satisfactory scores on the enumerated skills. These areas are necessary elements in capturing the mindsets of industries and sustained momentum equipped with potential job opportunities (Sia Kee Ming, 2010)

The desirability of the alumni in business administration to take further studies exemplifies a vast understanding to "kaizen" or continuous learning. Though, it has a low percentage but this could be used as precedence to students and even the alumni about the importance of further education. Stoeker (1991) claimed about the essence of expanding academic capability of students as avenue for growth financially and socially.

A large number of the graduates have not taken their education to further studies as this could be ascribed to cost, time availability and lack of information. Considerably there is low percentage for those that are unemployed, but can be qualified as choice due to parenthood.

V. Conclusion

The study is an attempt by the faculty of the College of Business Administration to come up with updated information about its graduate for the last 10 years, school year 2005 – 2006 up to 2017 – 2018. The output of this endeavor catapults a resounding desire to address A C N's existing curriculum's asset and flaws, its responsiveness to the industries preference for employment such as the needed skills and competencies, and capability of its faculty. The need to devise a holistic curriculum should be a priority so that responsive and proactive academic programs are offered.

The responses of the 195 alumni on this graduate tracer study employed a consensus of information. They chose A C N due to its location, but beyond that practical reason is A C N's capability to offer the desired product needed by the society manifested career advancement, and competitive faculty. Furthermore, the outcome provided information of high acceptability to employment among the graduates of A C N as this reflects the ability of the school to respond to what the industry needs. A reasonable number of respondents typified that A C N graduates can perform managerial and supervisory functions.

The privilege enjoyed by the graduates to immediately land a job is an echo to adequate skills possessed by them. A very good response to the displayed skills and competencies proved that the graduates had already specialized of a certain attitude that prepared them to be employment ready. This project, A C N' College of Business Administration, a reputable program. With the constraints of the study where the respondents are already working in areas where internet connection is a problem hence not able to respond in as much as they want to thus may have affected the objectivity in the gathering of data.

Recommendation

Although the school's curriculum in the BSBA program is still at par with the need of the society, somehow, it is but proper for the college to continuously enhance its program suitable to regional and international standards. The study's output generated a bunch of information cognizant to acknowledging that A C N's College of Business Management have these qualities of being competitive with high educational standards.

Further, as provided in the result of the study, the researchers intend to propose the following;

Assumption College of Nabunturan will continuously adopt global practices that enhance student's capability to actively acknowledge the significance of the business courses, and at the same allow them to clearly understand their potential job destination.

Assumption College of Nabunturan and the stakeholders to come up with a systematic program that will help BSBA graduates passed professional examinations such as Civil Service Examination as gateway to employment in government of which, the College shall offer review sessions to students and alumni. Alongside with this, growing

numbers of BSBA / Commerce graduates took education units after graduation hence, it is recommended to offer in the curriculum an elective 18 education units.

Lastly, although unemployed alumni are quite low but still the College can formulate a program where the alumni even at home can still perform their learned skills by providing training programs like livelihood or any home-based opportunities. Additionally, the college shall provide them training tools on investment and financial literacy so that they can use their available technology at home.

References

- [1.] Abel, J and Deitz, R. (ND). The role of colleges and universities in building local human capital retrieve from https://www.newyorkfed.org/medialibrary/media/research/current_issues/ci17-6.pdf
- [2.] Aquino, A., Punongbayan, E., Macalaguim, L., Bauyon, S., Rodriguez, Jr., R., Quizon, G. (2016). Teacher Education Graduate Tracer Study from 2010 to 2014 in One State University in Batangas, Philippines retrieved from <https://www.apjmr.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/APJMR-2015-3.5.2.06.pdf>
- [3.] Gines, A. (2014). Tracer Study of PNU Graduates retrieved from http://www.ajcnet.com/journals/Vol_4_No_3_March_2014/10.pdf
- [4.] Miniano, C.M. (2008). Tracer study on Business Administration Graduates retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271446801_Tracer_Study_on_Business_Administration_Graduates
- [5.] Paulsen, M. B. (1990). College Choice: Understanding student enrollment behavior retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED333855>
- [6.] Ramirez, T., Cruz, L., and Alcantara, N. (2014). Tracer Study of RTU graduates: An Analysis retrieved <https://www.questia.com/library/journal/1P3-3236185791/tracer-study-of-rtu-graduates-an-analysis>
- [7.] Segismundo, M.C., Zacarias, M. (2017). LCUP's Contribution to the nation's human capital: A tracer study of MAED, MBA, and MABS Graduates, AY 2012 - 2013 to 2015 - 2016 retrieved from <http://www.ijern.com/journal/2017/October-2017/18.pdf>
- [8.] Sia KeeMing., J. (2010). Institutional factors influencing students' College choice decision in Malaysia: A Conceptual Framework retrieved from http://www.ijbssnet.com/journals/Vol_1_No_3_December_2010/6.pdf
- [9.] Spearman, J., Abdul Rahim, M., Ghanayem, S., and Ljepava, N. (2016). Factors influencing student enrollment and choice of University. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/303960980_Factors_influencing_student_enrollment_and_choice_of_university
- [10.] Stoeker, J. (1991). Factors influencing the decision to return to graduate schools for professional students retrieved from https://www.jstor.org/stable/40196013?seq=1#page_scan_tab_contents
- [11.] Tanzharikova, A.Z. (2012). The Role of Higher Education system in human capital formation retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/3dd3/f9bf647cafd9fc0cef0b4fda4510edc2a4de.pdf>